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A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF SELECTED INDIAN PRIVATE SECTOR BANKS

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ABSTRACT

Indian Banks play important role in economic growth and development of country. After the privatization of bank, Indian bank, country shows the high growth in economy activities. After the privatization, Indian banking sector open for the private players. Private sector banks are now major tools of financial system. Private sector banks show that financial needs of country can be satisfied with efficient and fast way. Now, financial services can be easily assessable in every corner of country by private and public sector banks. Today, bank means not only deposit-withdrawal of money but more beyond deposit-withdrawal. Financial performance of a bank is not only important to management of bank but also important for many stakeholders. Many stakeholders' interest has connected with the performance of banks. Therefore, present study has been conducted to know the financial performance and health of selected private sector banks through ratio and percentages analysis. In India, several private banks operating but present study only limited to top 5 private banks i.e. ICICI Bank, Axis Bank, HDFC Bank, Yes Bank and Indusland Bank. Time period for study is taken from financial year 2010-11 to 2014-15. Data collected for study purpose is purely secondary in nature and collected manly from annual report of banks, journals, thesis, published documents and relevant websites.

For testing of hypothesis, Kruskal Wallis test has been employed with help of SPSS research software.

KEYWORDS: Private sector banks, Financial Performance, Kruskal Wallis test.

INTRODUCTION

Indian Banks play important role in economic growth and development of country. After the privatization of bank, Indian bank, country shows the high growth in economy activities. After the privatization, Indian banking sector open for the private players. Private sector banks are now major tools of financial system. Private sector banks show that financial needs of country can be satisfied with efficient and fast way. Now, financial services can be easily assessable in every corner of country by private and public sector banks. Today, bank means not only deposit-withdrawal of money but more beyond deposit-withdrawal. Financial performance of a bank is not only important to management of bank but also important for many stakeholders. Many stakeholders' interest has connected with the performance and financial health of banks.

Table 1: Total number of branches of selected bank

Year	Total No. of Branches									
	Banks									
	ICICI Bank	AGR (%)	Axis Bank	AGR (%)	HDFC Bank	AGR (%)	Yes Bank	AGR (%)	Indusland Bank	AGR (%)
2010-11	2529	-	1390	-	1986	-	214	-	300	-
2011-12	2752	8.82	1622	16.69	2544	28.10	356	66.36	400	33.3
2012-13	3100	12.65	1947	20.04	3062	20.36	430	20.79	500	25.0
2013-14	3753	21.06	2402	23.37	3403	11.14	560	30.23	602	20.4
2014-15	4050	7.91	2589	7.79	4014	17.95	630	12.50	801	33.0

Table 1 show the status of total number of branches of ICICI, Axis and HDFC Bank, Yes Bank and Indusland Bank. It shows that total number of branch of all bank are increasing year on year. ICICI Bank operates its business through 4050 branches in 2014-15. ICICI Bank has maximum number of branch and followed by HDFC Bank. Yes and Indusland Bank has minimum number of branch in last financial year. Above table also show that all banks engage to open more branches on year on year.

Figure 1: Trends in AGR of Total Number of Branches

Figure 1 shows the trends in AGR (Annual Growth Rate) in Total Number of Branches of ICICI, Axis and HDFC Banks Yes Bank and Indusland Bank. It shows that braches of all banks are increasing at steady rate. Annual growth rate is decreasing year on year. In the initial year of study all bank mark a high rate of growth in open new branches. But, passes of time, bank not maintaining high rate to open new branches. Figure also shows Yes Bank and

Indusland banks should allocate more funds to opens more branches for spread of its business.

Table 2: Total number of ATMs of selected Bank

Year	Total No. of ATMs									
	Banks									
	ICICI Bank	AGR (%)	Axis Bank	AGR (%)	HDFC Bank	AGR (%)	Yes Bank	AGR (%)	Indusland Bank	AGR (%)
2010-11	6055		6270		5471		247		586	
2011-12	9006	48.7	9924	58.2	8913	62.9	606	145.4	692	18.1
2012-13	10481	16.3	11245	13.3	10743	20.5	951	56.9	860	24.2
2013-14	11315	7.9	12922	14.9	11256	4.7	1,139	19.7	1110	29.6
2014-15	12451	10.0	12355	-4.3	11766	4.5	1,194	4.8	1,487	33.9

Table 2 shows the status of total number of ATMs of ICICI, Axis and HDFC Bank, Yes Bank and Indusland Bank. It shows that total numbers of ATMs of all banks are increasing year on year. ICICI Bank opens 12451 ATMs in different location to provide the facilities of ATMs. . ICICI Bank has maximum number of ATMs and followed by Axis Bank. Yes and Indusland Bank has minimum number of ATMs. Table also shows that banks are open ATMs on steady growth.

Figure 2: Trends in AGR of Total Number of ATMs

Figure 2 shows the trends in AGR (Annual Growth Rate) in Total Number of ATMs of ICICI, Axis and HDFC Banks Yes Bank and Indusland Bank. In the financial year 2011-12 all bank show high level of growth in open ATMs. Indusland bank ATMs growth in the year 2011-12 is 145.34% followed by HDFC Bank, Axis Bank, ICICI Bank, Indusland Bank, 62.91%, 58.28%, 48.74%, 18.09% respectively. But after financial year 2011-12 all banks show decreasing trends in open new ATMs except Indusland Bank show increasing trends. In the financial year 2014-15, Axis Bank shows -4.3% growths in total ATMs. Overall performance of banks is good in term of open new ATMs.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Review of literature is an important part of a research study. It like a magnify glass which can see problem in broad and clear vision. Literature review provides research gape to researcher. Review of literature also assist to researcher to choose what type of research methodology can be use to solve the problem and in the past what was the implication of past studies on present studies. There have vast literature on financial performance of commercial banks.

Makesh (2008) conduct a study to evaluate the financial management practices of Federal Bank, Dhanalakshmi Bank along with the SBI, for the financial year 2006-2007. His study revealed that all the three banks maintained capital in excess of the stipulated norms (Basel I, II & III) of the Reserve Bank of India. Federal Bank had maintained it in efficient way compare to its rivals. Dhanalakshmi Bank maintained a very high liquidity to tackle short-term needs of finance. But Federal Bank performed well in term of cost management compared to the SBI and Dhanalakshmi Bank.

Mabwe Kumbirai & Robert Webb (2010) tried to investigate the financial ratio analysis of commercial in South Africa. They employed financial ratios to measure the profitability, liquidity and credit quality performance of five large South African based commercial banks. They opinions that overall performance of bank is increase considerably in the first two year of the analysis. A significant change in trend is noticed at the onset of the global financial crisis in 2007, reaching its peak during 2008-2009. This resulted in falling profitability, low liquidity and deteriorating credit quality in the South African Banking sector.

Sharma (2010) tried to assess the bank failure resolution mechanism to analyze the powers given by the countries to their regulators to carry out resolution of failed banks among 148 countries during 2003. She employed twelve variables for correlation and regression analysis. Her study showed that the countries which had faced systemic crisis were more prone to providing liquidation powers to their regulators. These countries had a tendency to protect their regulators through immunity, rather than any legal action.

K T Srinivas (2013) conducted a study to measure the status of non-performing assets in commercial banks in India. He analyzed the non-performing of assets of commercials banks from 1996-97 to 2011-12. His opinion that there have many causes of non-performing asset

in commercial banks i.e. natural calamities, recession, changes in government policies, changes in economic conditions, internal defaulters, faulty projects etc. He found that the Gross Non-Performing Assets (GNPAs) of Nationalized Banks as on June 2012 were Rs.73038 crore which amount to 2.94% of Gross Advances.

Gilbert Sebe-Yeboah & Charles Mensah (2014) also conducted a research study to measure and compare the financial performance of agricultural development banks in Ghana. The PELARI (Profitability, Efficiency, Liquidity, Asset Quality, Risk Measures and Investor analyses) model was developed for analysis by the researcher which is similar to the CAMELS' rating. Troubled signals models such as the Altman z-score for non manufacturing companies and risk index were also used to measure risk. In this study, they found that bank's liquidity is decreasing very fast.

Cheenu Goel & Chitwan Bhutani (2013) also tried to compare the financial performance of public sector and private sector banks in India. They take a sample of three major public sector banks and three major private sector banks for study. They compare the financial performance of banks from the financial year 2009 to 2012. They used the judgmental sampling. They also employed ratio and coefficient correlation for analysis and interpretation of data. They concluded that new banks are more efficient than old banks. They also concluded that public sector banks are not as profitable as other sectors banks.

OBJECTIVE OF STUDY

- To study and compare the financial performance ICICI Bank, Axis Bank and HDFC Bank, Yes Bank and Indusland Bank through ratios analysis
- Try to find out which private sector bank performing better than other banks.
- Try to find out which private sector bank financial health is better.

HYPOTHESIS OF STUDY

The hypothesis of the present study is:

- $H_{0,1}$ Return on Net worth Ratio of selected banks is identical.
- $H_{a,1}$ Return on Net worth Ratio of selected banks is not identical.

- $H_{0,2}$ Capital Adequacy Ratio of selected banks is identical.
- $H_{a,2}$ Capital Adequacy Ratio of selected banks is not identical.

- $H_{0,3}$ Net NPAs to Net Advance Ratio of selected banks is identical.
- $H_{a,3}$ Net NPAs to Net Advance Ratio of selected Banks is not identical.

- $H_{0,4}$ Total Advance to total Deposit Ratio of selected banks is identical.
- $H_{a,4}$ Total Advance to total Deposit Ratio of selected banks is not identical.

- H_{0.5} Liquid Assets to Total Assets Ratio of selected banks is identical.
- Ha_{.5} Liquid Assets to Total Assets Ratio of selected banks is not identical.

- H_{0.6} Percentage growth in net profit of selected banks is identical.
- Ha_{.6} Percentage growth in net profit of selected banks is not identical.

- H_{0.7} Profit Per Employee of selected banks is identical.
- Ha_{.7} Profit Per Employee of selected banks is not identical.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In India, banks can be divided mainly into two sector one public and second private sector. Present study has conducted to evaluate and compare the financial performance and health of selected private sector banks. Total 23 private sector banks work in India, out of 23 only top 5 banks has selected for research study namely ICICI Bank, Axis Bank, HDFC Bank, Yes Bank and Indusland Bank. Judgmental sampling has been adopted for selection of banks for study. Ratio and percentage method are adopted for analysis of financial health of banks. Present study based on purely secondary data that has been collected from annual reports of selected banks, magazines, articles published in journals, other published documents and websites have been chosen when found relevant. The study covers the period of 5 years i.e. year 2010-11 to year 2014-15. It is known for the literature review that most of the past studies made on financial performance of commercial banks based on different financial variables such like Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE) and Return on Capital (ROC). To test the hypothesis Kruskal Wallis test has been employed with the help of SPSS statistical software. Output generated in analysis and interpretation section has been with the help of SPSS.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

Table 3: Return on Net worth Ratio of selected banks

Year	Return on Net Worth Ratio				
	Banks				
	ICICI Bank	Axis Bank	HDFC Bank	Yes Bank	Indusland Bank
2010-11	9.35	17.84	15.47	19.17	14.28
2011-12	10.70	18.60	17.27	20.89	16.97
2012-13	12.48	15.64	18.57	22.40	13.93
2013-14	13.40	16.27	19.50	22.72	15.59
2014-15	13.90	16.47	16.47	17.17	16.87
Mean	11.97	16.96	17.46	20.47	15.53

Source: Compile from annual report of selected banks

Table 3 shows the return on net worth ratio of selected banks. Yes Bank mean net worth ratio is highest compare to its rival bank and ICICI Bank mean net worth ratio is lowest. During the study period net worth ratio of all banks is fluctuating.

Testing of Hypothesis for Return on Net worth Ratio of selected banks

Ranks

	Private sector banks	N	Mean Rank
Return on Net Worth Ratio	ICICI Bank	5	3.00
	Axis Bank	5	14.30
	HDFC Bank	5	15.70
	Yes Bank	5	21.80
	Indusland Bank	5	10.20
	Total	25	

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	Return on Net Worth Ratio
Chi-Square	17.939
Df	4
Asymp. Sig.	.001

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable: Private sector banks

Above output has been generated with the help of SPSS. Calculating value of K-statistics is $17.939 >$ table value of K-statistics 13.277 at 1% level of significance which indicate Return on Net worth Ratio of selected banks is not identical. So, the null hypothesis “ $H_{0.1}$ Return on Net worth Ratio of selected banks is identical.” is rejected and there have enough statistical evidence to accept alternate hypothesis. It concluded that at 1% level of significance Return on Net worth Ratio of selected banks are not same. It also confirm from the p-value which is $.001 < \alpha=0.01$. It also inferred from the mean rank that Yes Bank, HDFC Bank and Axis Bank financial performance in term of net worth ratio is good compare to ICICI Bank and Indusland Bank.

Table 4: Capital Adequacy Ratio of selected banks

Year	Capital Adequacy Ratio				
	Banks				
	ICICI Bank	Axis Bank	HDFC Bank	Yes Bank	Indusland Bank
2010-11	19.54	12.65	16.22	16.50	15.89
2011-12	18.52	13.66	16.52	17.90	13.85
2012-13	18.74	17.00	16.80	18.30	15.36
2013-14	17.70	16.07	16.07	14.40	13.83
2014-15	17.02	15.09	16.79	15.60	12.09
Mean	18.30	14.89	16.48	16.54	14.20

Source: Compile from annual report of selected banks

Table 4 shows the capital adequacy ratio of selected banks. ICICI Bank mean net worth ratio is highest compare to its rival bank and Indusland Bank mean capital adequacy ratio is lowest. Table also shows that mean CAR of HDFC bank and Yes Bank is approximately equal and also good. CAR of ICICI Bank, HDFC Bank, Yes Bank try to show better financial health of banks in eye of its depositors.

Testing of Hypothesis for Capital Adequacy Ratio of selected banks

Ranks		N	Mean Rank
	Private sector banks		
Capital Adequacy Ratio	ICICI Bank	5	22.20
	Axis Bank	5	8.30
	HDFC Bank	5	14.50
	Yes Bank	5	14.40
	Indusland Bank	5	5.60
	Total	25	

Test Statistics ^{a,b}	
	Capital Adequacy Ratio
Chi-Square	15.301
df	4
Asymp. Sig.	.004

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable: Private sector banks

Above output has been generated with the help of SPSS. Calculating value of K-statistics is 15.301 > table value of K-statistics 13.277 at 1% level of significance which indicate Capital Adequacy Ratio of selected banks is not identical. So, the null hypothesis “H_{0,2} Capital Adequacy Ratio of selected banks is identical.” is rejected and there have enough statistical evidence to accept alternate hypothesis. It also concluded that at 1% level of significance Capital Adequacy Ratio of selected banks are not same. It also confirm from the p-value which is .004 < α=0.01. It also inferred from the mean rank that ICICI, HDFC Bank and Yes Bank financial performance in term of Capital Adequacy Ratio is good compare to Axis Bank and Indusland Bank.

Table 5: Net NPA to Net Advance Ratio of selected banks

Year	Net NPA's to Net Advances (%)				
	Banks				
	ICICI Bank	Axis Bank	HDFC Bank	Yes Bank	Indusland Bank
2010-11	1.11	0.29	0.19	0.03	0.28
2011-12	0.73	0.28	0.18	0.05	0.27
2012-13	0.77	0.36	0.20	0.01	0.31
2013-14	0.97	0.44	0.27	0.05	0.33
2014-15	1.61	0.46	0.25	0.12	0.31
Mean	1.04	0.37	0.22	0.05	0.30

Source: Compile from annual report of selected banks

Table 5 shows the Net NPA's to Net Advances ratio of selected banks. Above table shows that mean Net NPA's to Net Advances ratio of Yes Bank is lowest which indicates Yes Bank advances are in safe hands. Table also shows that ICICI bank mean Net NPA's to Net Advances ratio is highest which indicates ICICI Bank suffering the problem of blockage of assets. Net NPA's to Net Advances ratio of HDFC, Axis and Indusland is good.

Testing of Hypothesis for Net NPA's to Net Advances (%)

Ranks		N	Mean Rank
Net NPA's to Net Advances (%)	Private sector banks		
	ICICI Bank	5	23.00
	Axis Bank	5	16.70
	HDFC Bank	5	8.10
	Yes Bank	5	3.00
	Indusland Bank	5	14.20
Total		25	

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	Net NPA's to Net Advances (%)
Chi-Square	22.108
df	4
Asymp. Sig.	.000

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable: Private sector banks

Above output has been generated with the help of SPSS. Calculating value of K-statistics is 22.108 > table value of K-statistics 13.277 at 1% level of significance which indicate Net NPA's to Net Advances Ratio of selected banks is not identical. So, the null hypothesis “H₀ H_{0,3} Net NPAs to Net Advance Ratio of selected banks is identical.” is rejected and there have enough statistical evidence to accept alternate hypothesis. It also concluded that at 1% level of significance Net NPAs to Net Advance Ratio of selected banks are not same. It also confirm from the p-value which is .000 < α=0.01. It also inferred from the mean rank, Yes Bank, HDFC Bank and Indusland Bank financial performance in term of assets management is good compare to ICICI Bank and Axis Bank.

Table 6: Total Advance to total Deposit Ratio of selected banks

Year	Total Advances to Total Deposits Ratio				
	Banks				
	ICICI Bank	Axis Bank	HDFC Bank	Yes Bank	Indusland Bank
2010-11	0.96	0.75	0.77	0.75	0.76
2011-12	0.99	0.77	0.79	0.77	0.83
2012-13	0.99	0.78	0.81	0.70	0.82
2013-14	0.95	0.82	0.82	0.75	0.91
2014-15	0.99	0.87	0.81	0.83	0.93
Mean	0.98	0.80	0.80	0.76	0.85

Source: Compile from annual report of selected banks

Table 6 shows the Total Advance to total Deposit Ratio of selected banks. Above table shows mean Total Advances to Total Deposits Ratio of ICICI bank is highest which means ICICI

bank is highly flexible to provide advances to loan seeker. Mean Total Advances to Total Deposits Ratio of Axis and HDFC is same during the study period which both banks also flexible to provide advances to loan seekers. Indusland bank also provides 85% advance out of total deposit.

Testing of Hypothesis for Total Advance to total Deposit Ratio of selected banks

Ranks				Test Statistics ^{a,b}	
	Private sector banks	N	Mean Rank		Total Advances to Total Deposits Ratio
Total Advances to Total Deposits Ratio	ICICI Bank	5	23.00	Chi-Square	15.235
	Axis Bank	5	10.20	df	4
	HDFC Bank	5	10.80	Asymp. Sig.	.004
	Yes Bank	5	6.10		
	Indusland Bank	5	14.90		
	Total	25			

a. Kruskal Wallis Test
b. Grouping Variable: Private sector banks

Above output has been generated with the help of SPSS. Calculating value of K-statistics is 15.235 > table value of K-statistics 13.277 at 1% level of significance which indicate Total Advance to total Deposit Ratio of selected banks is not identical. So, the null hypothesis “H_{0,4} Total Advance to total Deposit Ratio of selected banks is identical.” is rejected and there have enough statistical evidence to accept alternate hypothesis. It also confirm from the p-value .004 which is less than $\alpha=0.01$. It also inferred from the mean rank, ICICI Bank and Indusland Bank financial are highly flexible compare to Yes Bank, HDFC Bank and Axis Bank.

Table 7: Liquid Assets to Total Assets Ratio of selected banks

Year	Liquid Assets to Total Assets Ratio				
	Banks				
	ICICI Bank	Axis Bank	HDFC Bank	Yes Bank	Indusland Bank
2010-11	0.08	0.09	0.11	0.06	0.09
2011-12	0.08	0.05	0.06	0.05	0.10
2012-13	0.08	0.06	0.07	0.04	0.09
2013-14	0.07	0.07	0.08	0.05	0.08
2014-15	0.07	0.08	0.06	0.06	0.10
Mean	0.07	0.07	0.08	0.05	0.09

Source: Compile from annual report of selected banks

Table 7 shows the Liquid Assets to Total Assets Ratio of selected banks. Mean LATA ratio of Indusland Bank is highest during the period of study which indicates Indusland Bank is

more capable to tackle short-term liabilities. Mean LATA ratio of HDFC Bank, ICICI Bank and Axis Bank approximately equal and these bank also able to meet short-term need of finance easily. Mean LATA ratio of Yes bank is lowest among banks which indicate Yes Bank may face problem to tackle short-term need of finance.

Testing of Hypothesis for Liquid Assets to Total Assets Ratio of selected banks

Ranks			
	Private sector banks	N	Mean Rank
Liquid Assets to Total Assets Ratio	ICICI Bank	5	14.50
	Axis Bank	5	11.80
	HDFC Bank	5	13.40
	Yes Bank	5	4.20
	Indusland Bank	5	21.10
	Total	25	

Test Statistics ^{a,b}	
	Liquid Assets to Total Assets Ratio
Chi-Square	13.957
Df	4
Asymp. Sig.	.007

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable: Private sector banks

Above output has been generated with the help of SPSS. Calculating value of K-statistics is 13.957 > table value of K-statistics 13.277 at 1% level of significance which indicate Liquid Assets to Total Assets Ratio of selected banks is not identical. So, the null hypothesis “Liquid Assets to Total Assets Ratio of selected banks is identical.” is rejected and there have enough statistical evidence to accept alternate hypothesis. It also confirm from the p-value .007 which is less than $\alpha=0.01$. It also inferred from the mean rank Indusland Bank, ICICI Bank, HDFC Bank have more strong to tackle short-term capital needs compare to Yes Bank, and Axis Bank.

Table 8: Percentage growth in net profit of selected banks

Year	Percentage Growth in net profit				
	Banks				
	ICICI Bank	Axis Bank	HDFC Bank	Yes Bank	Indusland Bank
2010-11	27.99	34.76	33.16	52.21	64.80
2011-12	25.51	25.19	31.60	34.40	39.02
2012-13	28.77	22.09	30.25	33.13	32.22
2013-14	17.84	20.05	26.00	24.40	32.68
2014-15	13.91	18.34	20.50	23.96	27.39
Mean	22.80	24.09	28.30	33.62	39.22

Source: Compile from annual report of selected banks

Table 8 shows the Percentage growth in net profit of selected banks. Mean percentage growth in net profit is highest for Indusland but it decreasing year on year that is cause of problem

for Indusland bank. Percentage growth in net profit of Yes and HDFC bank also good but these banks also show the decreasing trend. Percentage growth in net profit of ICICI bank is lowest among all banks. Percentage growth in net profit of Indusland and Yes Bank shows that finance performance of these better than others banks. In the year 2010-11 all bank shows remarkable growth in net profits.

Testing of Hypothesis for Percentage growth in net profit of selected banks

Ranks			
	Private sector banks	N	Mean Rank
Percentage Growth in net profit	ICICI Bank	5	8.00
	Axis Bank	5	8.80
	HDFC Bank	5	13.40
	Yes Bank	5	15.80
	Indusland Bank	5	19.00
	Total		25

Test Statistics^{a,b}	
	Percentage Growth in net profit
Chi-Square	7.998
df	4
Asymp. Sig.	.092

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable: Private sector banks

Above output has been generated with the help of SPSS. Calculating value of K-statistics is 7.998 < table value of K-statistics 13.277 at 1% level of significance which indicate percentage growth in net profit of selected banks is identical. So, the null hypothesis “Percentage growth in net profit of selected banks is identical.” is accepted and there have enough statistical evidence to reject alternate hypothesis. It also confirm from the p-value .092 which is more than $\alpha=0.01$. It also inferred from the mean rank Indusland Bank, Yes Bank is generating profit at higher rate compare to others commercial banks.

Table 9: Profit Per Employee of selected banks

Year	Profit Per Employee				
	Banks				
	ICICI Bank	Axis Bank	HDFC Bank	Yes Bank	Indusland Bank
2010-11	10.00	14.00	7.37	20.89	8.24
2011-12	11.00	14.00	8.00	20.42	8.57
2012-13	11.00	15.00	10.00	21.02	9.22
2013-14	14.00	15.00	12.00	20.45	9.03
2014-15	16.00	17.00	10.00	20.96	9.38
Mean	12.40	15.00	9.47	20.75	8.89

Source: Compile from annual report of selected banks

Table 9 shows the Profit Per Employee of selected banks. Mean profit per employee of Yes Bank and Axis Bank is highest during study period compare to others banks. Indusland Bank and HDFC Bank profit per employee is lowest. Yes Bank and Axis Bank financial performance in term of profit per employee is remarkable and Indusland bank and HDFC Bank should motivate its employee to generate more business that will increase more profits.

Testing of Hypothesis for Profit Per Employee of selected banks

Ranks				Test Statistics ^{a,b}	
	Private sector banks	N	Mean Rank		Profit Per Employee
Profit Per Employee	ICICI Bank	5	13.20	Chi-Square	20.245
	Axis Bank	5	17.00	Df	4
	HDFC Bank	5	6.80	Asymp. Sig.	.000
	Yes Bank	5	23.00		
	Indusland Bank	5	5.00		
	Total	25			

a. Kruskal Wallis Test
b. Grouping Variable: Private sector banks

Above output has been generated with the help of SPSS. Calculating value of K-statistics is 20.245 > table value of K-statistics 13.277 at 1% level of significance which indicate for Profit Per Employee of selected banks is not identical. So, the null hypothesis “H_{0.7} Profit Per Employee of selected banks is identical.” is rejected and there have enough statistical evidence to accept alternate hypothesis. It also confirm from the p-value .000 which is less than $\alpha=0.01$. It also inferred from the mean rank Yes Bank and Axis Bank employees are more capable to generate more profit compare to other banks.

CONCLUSION

It is very difficult for research to measure the financial performance of banks in such a dynamic environment where everything is changing at rapidly rate. A bank has not work only in limited boundary but also face various types of international movement in financial market. A bank performance affected by various types of factors like monetary policies of central bank, fiscal policies of central and state government, inflation rate, attitude of management, worker efficiency, technology etc from time to time. Bank works in changing and competitive environment. Despite external environment, some important conclusion have draw.

It concluded from the return on net worth ratio that Yes bank, HDFC bank and Axis bank generated more return on net worth compare to ICICI and Indusland bank. Capital Adequacy Ratio show that ICICI Bank, HDFC Bank and Yes bank enjoy the high capital availability than Axis Bank and Indusland Bank

Yes Bank and HDFC Bank asset management is very smart to manage the assets than ICICI, Axis and Indusland bank. ICICI Bank the Net NPA's to Net Advances ratio is very high come to its rival.

ICICI bank is very flexible to provide advances to seekers and other banks are provide advances around 80-85% of total deposit. High Advance to total Deposit Ratio of ICICI bank could be one of causes for high NPAs to others banks.

It also concluded from the study that Mean LATA ratio of Indusland Bank is highest during the period of study which indicates Indusland Bank is more capable to tackle short-term liabilities. Mean LATA ratio of HDFC Bank, ICICI Bank and Axis Bank approximately equal and these bank also able to meet short-term need of finance easily.

Research study also indicate that Indusland Bank and Yes Bank generated profit high rate than ICICI Bank, Axis Bank and HDFC Bank. It can also conclude from the research article that Yes Bank and Axis Bank financial performance in term of profit per employee is remarkable and Indusland bank and HDFC Bank should motivate its employee to generate more business that will increase more profits.

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